

GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT MILESTONE IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OF LIPA CITY: AN ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

Gender issues and concerns, like gender equality, equity, and biases are obvious. The problems between sex and gender are getting worse. It searches to realize gender equality as a fundamental value that ought to be reflected in development choices and contends that women are active agents of development, not just passive recipients of development (PCW, 2011). The purpose of the study is to guide the school GAD focal persons geared a GAD plan which should be very aware of the emerging needs of their clients. To assess the milestone of gender and development to assist in future trainings and can be very substantial in designing the various projects, activities and programs associated with this issue. This study determined the issues arising within the implementation of gender and development and can identify the gaps. A quantitative method of research was used in data analysis for it elicit the substantial information necessary to the study. Purposive sampling was used since it is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. Respondents were the GAD focal person in each school. Questionnaire was adopted from the GMEF Organizational Assessment. Findings revealed that all schools do not involve in research with respect to gender and development and collection of sex-disaggregated data (SDD) was not visible. It was also found out that there was a minimal review of existing policies for consistency with emerging GAD issues. It showed that there were still School's GAD Focal Point System members who were not able to attend appropriate and relevant training and GAD corner among schools is not observable. Schools play a vital role in the implementation of Gender and Development (GAD) advocacies. It was concluded that, the milestone of SDO Lipa City in GAD matters implies slight difference from what is expected when it comes to people, policy, enabling mechanisms and PPAs. The GAD focal person does not show much attention to meet the standards. The GAD focal point system exerted less effort to strengthen these indicators.

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